

BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Rabiul Awal

Research Scholar,

Department of Education, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

Abstract:

Biodiversity is the collective term for the full variety of life on earth. It refers not just to species but also about the genetic diversity within species, the diversity of habitats and also the large biological units which is known as biomes e.g. grassland, tropical forests etc. Biodiversity provides people with basic ecosystem goods such as food, fibre and medicine, and services such as air and water purification, climate regulation, erosion control and nutrient cycling. Biodiversity also plays an important role in economic sectors that drive development, including agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism. Biodiversity is essential for sustainable development and human well-being. Biodiversity is currently being lost at up to 1,000 times the natural rate due to the loss of habitat, over-exploitation of resources, climate change, pollution, invasive exotic species, diseases, hunting etc. Since it provides us with several economic and ethical benefits and aesthetic values it is very important to conserve biodiversity. Biodiversity conservation is the protection and management of biodiversity to obtain resources for sustainable development. Biodiversity conservation and sustainable development both are interrelated branches focusing on social progress, economic growth & environmental protection on one side and ecosystem conservation on the other side. To use biodiversity in a sustainable manner means to use natural resources at a rate that the earth can renew them. There are different strategies and timeframes for achieving similar goals which are discussed in this paper.

Key words: *Biodiversity, Conservation, Ecosystem, Adaptive management, Sustainable development*

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/amierj/>

Introduction

The biodiversity of an ecosystem contributes to the sustainability of that ecosystem. The higher the biodiversity of an ecosystem, the more sustainable it is. Conversely, lower biodiversity equals less sustainability. The higher biodiversity in an ecosystem means that there is a greater variety of genes and species in that ecosystem. A great variety of genes and species means that the ecosystem is better able to carry out natural processes (such as biogeochemical cycles, population dynamics, evolution, succession, etc.) in the face of external stress. The more sustainable an ecosystem is the better it is for the environment and for people. This is because we need ecosystems to survive - we need nutrients, food, medicine and money to survive and ecosystems provide us with all of these things. So, it is in everyone's best interest to increase the sustainability of ecosystems. Biodiversity and ecosystems feature prominently across many of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and associated targets. They contribute directly to human well-being and development priorities. Biodiversity is at the centre of many economic activities, particularly those related to crop and livestock agriculture, forestry, and fisheries. Globally, nearly half of the human population is directly dependent on natural resources for its livelihood, and many of the most vulnerable people depend directly on biodiversity to fulfil their daily subsistence needs.

Biodiversity

Biodiversity thus includes not only the millions of different species on Earth, it also consists of the specific genetic variations and traits within species (such as different crop varieties), as well as the various types of different ecosystems, marine and terrestrial, in which human societies live and on which they depend, such as coastal areas, forests, wetlands, grasslands, mountains and deserts. Biodiversity is essential for sustainable development and human well-being. It underpins the provision of food, fibre and water; it mitigates and provides resilience to climate change; it supports human health, and provides jobs in agriculture, fisheries, forestry and many other sectors. Without effective measures to conserve biodiversity and use its components in a sustainable manner, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development will not be achievable.

Sustainable Development

Sustainable human development is about living on Earth without taking more than can be naturally replaced. Sustainable development is about improving the quality of human life while living within the carrying capacity of supporting ecosystems (IUCN & UNEP).

It is about good health, good living conditions and long-term wealth creation for everybody. All these things must occur within the carrying capacity of the planet. To understand sustainable development, think about its three pillars: “economic wealth”, “social equity” and “environmental health”; or in other words “profit”, “people” and “planet”. All three are linked to each other. In other words, any development has to be not only economically sound but also beneficial to social equity and environmental health.

Biodiversity Conservation to Sustainable Development

Biodiversity provides people with basic ecosystem goods and services. It provides goods such as food, fibre and medicine, and services such as air and water purification, climate regulation, erosion control and nutrient cycling. Biodiversity also plays an important role in economic sectors that drive development, including agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism. More than three billion people rely on marine and coastal biodiversity, and 1.6 billion people rely on forests and non-timber forest products (e.g. the fruits from trees) for their livelihoods. Many people depend directly on the availability of usable land, water, plants and animals to support their families. In fact, ecosystems are the base of all economies.

Role of Biodiversity in achieving Sustainable Development Goals

SDG 1 – End poverty in all its forms everywhere

Biodiversity provides resources and income, particularly for the rural poor. Ecosystem services and other non-marketed goods make up between 50% and 90% of the total source of livelihoods among poor rural and forest-dwelling households.

SDG 2 – End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition; promote sustainable agriculture

Biodiversity is a key element of food security and a means of improving nutrition. Many of the most vulnerable people depend on food gathered from natural ecosystems, such as forests, grasslands, oceans and rivers. Biodiversity also underpins ecosystem functions, such as pollination and the maintenance of soil fertility, and water quality, central to agricultural productivity.

SDG 3 – Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages

Nearly 1 in 4 deaths globally is attributed to environmental risk factors. Healthy ecosystems help mitigate the spread and impact of pollution by both sequestering and eliminating certain types of air, water and soil pollution. Agricultural biodiversity

contributes to increased sustainable production, reducing the need for pesticides and other chemical inputs, resulting in benefits to human health. Further, a substantial proportion of the world's population depends on traditional medicines derived from biodiversity for their health care needs.

SDG 5 – Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

Women play a vital role in agriculture, nutrition and the well-being of families and communities. Recognizing women's roles as key land and natural resource managers is central to sustainable development. In addition, loss of biodiversity and associated ecosystem services can perpetuate gender inequalities by increasing the time spent by women and children in performing certain tasks, such as collecting valuable resources, including fuel, food and water.

SDG 6 – Ensure the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

Ecosystems help maintain water supply and quality, and guard against water-related hazards and disasters. For example, wetlands play a role in surface, subsurface and ground water storage, and reduce the risk of flooding. They also help capture, process and dilute pollutants. Similarly, vegetation, such as grasslands and forests, supports the healthy functioning of watersheds. Managing ecosystems to maintain these types of services is generally more cost-effective than employing built technologies.

SDG 8 – Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

Biodiversity and ecosystems underpin many national and global economic activities, including those related to agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture, energy, tourism, transport and trade. Biodiversity conservation and sustainable use can lead to higher productivity, more efficient resource use, and long-term viability of resources.

SDG 9 – Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

Biodiversity and healthy ecosystems can provide reliable and cost-effective natural infrastructure. For example, coral reefs and mangrove forests protect coasts against flooding that are expected to increase with climate change. Natural infrastructure such as vegetation in cities can reduce the run-off of pollution into water bodies. Such green infrastructure can offer multiple benefits and are often more effective than built infrastructure in terms of cost, longevity and effectiveness.

SDG 11 – Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable

Ecosystems and biodiversity underpin the day-to-day functioning of human settlements by delivering the basic services and conditions that enable, support and protect human production, consumption and habitation. Biological resources provide many of the foods, building materials, energy and medicines consumed in urban centres. Urban planning that integrates biodiversity considerations can contribute to more sustainable, cost-effective and healthy human settlements.

SDG 12 – Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns

Consumption and production of all goods and services require the transformation of many natural resources, which in turn impacts biodiversity. Current unsustainable consumption and production patterns can undermine the ability of ecosystems to provide services for industries and communities that rely upon them. Using cleaner and more resource-efficient approaches that minimize wastes and pollutants can bring about economic opportunities and better quality of life for consumers and producers alike, and at the same time benefit biodiversity.

SDG 13 – Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

Forests, peatlands, wetlands, ocean and coastal ecosystems represent globally significant carbon stores, and their conservation and sustainable use is a critical element for avoiding dangerous changes to the Earth’s atmospheric temperature and climate system. Efforts to protect and restore habitats offer cost-effective and proven ways to mitigate climate change. Such ecosystems can also serve as natural buffers against climate extremes and other disasters, and strengthen adaptation to climate change.

SDG 14 – Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development

The conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in marine and coastal ecosystems is a key aspect of sustainable development. Biodiversity underpins all fishing and aquaculture activities, as well as other species harvested for foods and medicines. Conservation and sustainable use of marine and coastal biodiversity is essential to ensure that the world’s oceans, seas and marine resources remain vital.

SDG 15 – Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss

The conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems is essential for sustainable development. Targets under this goal include a call to integrate ecosystem and biodiversity values into national and local development planning, poverty reduction strategies and accounts.

SDG 16 – Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels

Conflicts over natural resources, environmental degradation and contamination can be one of the factors leading to social insecurity and violence. Vulnerable people are often disproportionately affected. Strengthening community rights over natural resources management, combating illegal exploitation and corruption, and ensuring transparent decision-making on social and environmental issues constitute an important process toward building an inclusive society based on justice.

SDG 17 – Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

The Strategic Plan for Biodiversity provides opportunities for strengthening global partnership on science, technology and innovation, dissemination of environmentally sound technologies, and for building national capacity for monitoring the progress of the 2030 Agenda.

Biodiversity Conservation

Biodiversity conservation means protection, conservation and management of biodiversity in order to obtain sustainable benefits for future generations. Biodiversity conservation is the protection, upliftment and management of biodiversity to obtain resources for sustainable development.

Importance of Biodiversity Conservation

It is believed that an area with higher species abundance has a more stable environment compared to an area with lower species abundance. We can further claim the necessity of biodiversity by considering our degree of dependency on the environment. We depend directly on various species of plants for our various needs. Similarly, we depend on various species of animals and microbes for different reasons. Biodiversity is being lost due to the loss of habitat, over-exploitation of resources, climatic changes, pollution, invasive exotic species, diseases, hunting, etc. Since it provides us with several economic and ethical benefits and adds aesthetic value, it is very important to conserve biodiversity.

Biodiversity conservation is important because biodiversity provides certain services and resources that are essential for life on earth. Biodiversity also provides social benefits.

Biodiversity conservation has three main objectives:-

- To preserve the diversity of species.
- Sustainable utilization of species and ecosystem.
- To maintain life-supporting systems and essential ecological processes.

Biodiversity can be conserved by:-

- Preventing the cutting of trees.
- Putting a ban on hunting of animals.
- Efficient utilisation of natural resources.
- Protected areas should be developed for animals where no human activities are allowed.

Strategies for Biodiversity Conservation

There is more than one way to conserve biodiversity which are as follows:-

1. In situ and ex situ conservation

In-situ conservation of biodiversity is the conservation of species within their natural habitat. In this method, the natural ecosystem is maintained and protected. The in-situ conservation has several advantages. Following are the important advantages of in-situ conservation:

- I. It is a cost-effective and convenient method of conserving biodiversity.
- II. A large number of living organisms can be conserved simultaneously.
- III. Since the organisms are in a natural ecosystem, they can evolve better and can easily adjust to different environmental conditions.

Certain protected areas where in-situ conservation takes place include national parks, wildlife sanctuaries and biosphere reserves.

Ex-situ conservation of biodiversity involves the breeding and maintenance of endangered species in artificial ecosystems such as zoos, nurseries, botanical gardens, gene banks, etc. There is less competition for food, water and space among the organisms.

Ex-situ conservation has the following advantages:

- I. The animals are provided with a longer time and breeding activity.
- II. The species bred in captivity can be reintroduced in the wild.
- III. Genetic techniques can be used for the preservation of endangered species.

2. Conservation on productive landscapes

While protected areas and parks remain a cornerstone for biodiversity conservation worldwide, conservation efforts are not limited to these places. Large productive landscapes with no specific conservation objective can contain lots of biodiversity while offering food, shelter and other ecosystem services for humanity. Agricultural lands, timber forests, grasslands, rivers and marine areas are productive landscapes that are also important for biodiversity. These landscapes are managed with the aim of producing and harvesting food, timber, energy and marine resources. Even though biodiversity conservation is not the main objective, the management of these landscapes must be sensitive to biodiversity. If it's not, resource exploitation can harm the long-term health of the ecosystem and its ability to supply food, timber, energy and other resources. This recognition has led to the promotion of sustainable agriculture, sustainable forestry, sustainable grassland management and sustainable fisheries.

3. Monitoring

Close monitoring of biodiversity is another important conservation practice; it involves regular checking of the overall health of ecosystems and the species living within it. The data collected from ongoing monitoring programmes can help inform management plans and improve the sustainability of activities in productive landscapes. Monitoring is especially important when the activities are carried out on an industrial scale because their impact is greater than the impact of similar activities carried out on a smaller subsistence scale by local communities.

4. Law and community enforcement

Conservation mechanisms may include law or community enforcement. Biodiversity conservation officers make sure the communities relying on the site's natural resources are totally involved in conservation initiatives. Officers enforce the laws and record the details of community participation. When the laws are not respected, illegal logging, mining and hunting erode the benefits of conservation efforts.

5. Traditional knowledge and practices

In many cases, traditional knowledge has contributed to protecting wildlife and ecosystems and to ensuring a "natural balance". According to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Traditional knowledge comprises of knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities around the world, developed from experience gained over centuries and adapted to the local culture and environment, which

is transmitted orally from generation to generation. Traditional knowledge is collectively owned and takes the form of stories, songs, folklore, proverbs, cultural values, beliefs, rituals, community laws, local languages and agricultural practices, including the development of plant species and animal breeds. Article 8(j) of the CBD calls for countries to respect, preserve and maintain knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.

Biodiversity conservation practitioners must therefore ensure that the communities relying directly on natural resources are involved in conservation initiatives, and guarantee their active participation during the whole conservation process. Some form of community engagement is essential for the success of any biodiversity conservation project. There are also many good examples of community conserved areas around the world. These sites have been managed by communities for generations for the sustainable use of natural resources such as medicinal plants and water springs, or even for religious purposes. These sites may or may not have government protection or written management regulations. However, the community members have developed well-recognised and respected rules that are often stronger than any law and have been practised for generations. The end result is the conservation and sustainable use of resources. Some governments now legally recognise traditional practices and treat indigenous and local communities as the customary stewards of the biodiversity.

6. Role of research & technology for biodiversity conservation

Biodiversity conservation doesn't happen in a vacuum. As we've seen, it requires the participation of many different groups of people, working with various conservation mechanisms both in-situ and ex-situ. Biodiversity policy and conservation activities are informed, enhanced and driven by research and technology. Researchers such as biologists, ecologists and social scientists play various roles in conservation. They identify species and their habitats, they locate areas of high ecological value, they pinpoint threats, and they propose innovative strategies and solutions. Researchers use various methods such as field surveys, observations and experiments, and technologies including remote sensing devices, data analyses, software and laboratory tests.

Research results are very important for biodiversity conservation. They can be woven into community development programmes. In fact, local communities can be important contributors to biodiversity conservation research, and should be involved in all steps of

the research and conservation processes. Research results are also used by conservation and development activists, journalists, government decision-makers and even businesses. The creation and application of technologies are also benefits of biodiversity conservation research. Technologies are invented, selected, evaluated, tested and applied to solve specific problems. Technologies can be transferred from rich countries to poor countries and vice versa; this process can be essential to community development. Before using any technology, however, it's critical to have a clear understanding of its characteristics so that the intervention does not harm local livelihoods, traditions, cultures or the environment.

7. Technological and management considerations for conservation in developing countries

Biodiversity conservation in developing countries has its own set of challenges. Not only are there natural issues, such as climate change and climate variability effects, but many local communities rely on the natural resources they harvest and hunt in protected areas. In these situations, it is especially important to ensure the management plans and technologies are considerate of community needs and capacities, and are endorsed by the affected communities.

Conclusion

Biodiversity conservation and sustainable development are two inter-related branches focusing on social progress, economic growth and environmental protection on one side, and ecosystem conservation on the other. Conservation includes the efforts carried out in protected areas such as national parks and community reserves, and in other areas with rich and important biodiversity where conservation is not the main focus. It is in these latter productive landscapes where sustainability is needed most. Sustainable agriculture, sustainable fisheries and sustainable management of natural resources are the main approaches for preserving these landscapes for long-term social, economic and ecological benefits. As the human population increases, so does the pressure on ecosystems, since we draw ever more resources from them. Our ecological foot print on the planet is unsustainable and will become unbearable unless we change our consumption patterns and our behaviour in general. It is the primary responsibility of human being to take corrective action against the damage caused by them and to improve biodiversity through scientific management because humans are the most beneficial species from almost all the benefits of biodiversity. There is more than one way (e.g. in-situ & ex-situ methods)

to conserve biodiversity. Today our only option is to manage productivity and resources in a sustainable manner, reducing waste wherever possible, using the principle of adaptive management and taking into account traditional knowledge which contributes to the maintenance of ecosystem services. Government must be commit themselves to integrate conservation and sustainable development use into their policies at the national level. By minimizing biodiversity loss and helping local populations restore degraded areas, together we can make this a new era of environmentally-sound economic development.

References

1. Malhotra, K.C., Stanley, S., Hemam, N.S. and Das, K. Biodiversity conservation and ethics: sacred groves and pools, 1997, 338-345
2. Singh, S.P. Himalayan forest ecosystem services: Incorporating in national accounting. Uttarakhand, India: Central Nainital, Himalayan Environment Association (CHEA) (9) 2007.
3. Samant, S.S., Dhar, U. and Rawal, R.S. Biodiversity status of a protected area in West Himalaya: Askot Wildlife Sanctuary. *The International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, **5**(3), 1998, 194- 203.
4. IUCN, G. IUCN red list of threatened species. Switzerland, Cambridge, UK: IUCN, Glands, 2003.
5. Walter, K.S. and Gillett, H.J. IUCN Red List of threatened plants. IUCN, 1998.
6. Meakin, S. The Rio earth summit: summary of the United Nations conference on environment and development, Library of Parliament, Research Branch, (317), 1992.
7. Singh, J.S. The biodiversity crisis: a multifaceted review. *Current Science*, **82**(6), 2002, 638-647.
8. The state of the world's plant genetic resources for food and agriculture, FAO, 1998.
9. Gallai, N. and Sales, J. 2009. Economic valuation of the vulnerability of world agriculture confronted with pollinator decline. *Ecological Economics*, (68), 2009, 810-82.
10. Forest survey of India, Government of India 1999.
11. Gaston., K.J. and Spicer, J.I. Biodiversity: An Introduction, 2nd Edition, Blackwell, 2004.
12. Grant, M. and Mitton, J.B. Even larger organisms. *Nature*, 1992, 360:216.
13. Wilson, E.O. Threats to biodiversity. *Scientific American* September, 1989, 108-116.

14. Zaffar, R., Noor, A. and Habib, B. Attitude of local people towards wildlife conservation, *International Mountain Society* (2), 2015, 68-77.
15. Saxena. NTFP policy and the poor in India. Planning Commission, New Delhi, 1999.
16. Manilal, K.S. Flora of silent valley tropical rain forests of India. The Mathrubhumi Press, Calicut, India, 1988, 398.

Internet Sources:

1. <https://unfoundation.org/blog/post/biodiversity-essential-sustainable-development/>
2. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/biodiversity/conservation>
3. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/intro/index_en.htm
4. <https://www.safeworldhse.com/2020/04/biodiversity-types-importance-loss-conservation.html>
5. https://www.biologicaldiversity.org/programs/population_and_sustainability/sustainability/live_more_sustainably.html
6. <https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/environment/5-important-measures-for-sustainable-development/9912>
7. <https://greentumble.com/10-ways-to-protect-biodiversity/>
8. <https://www.onlinebiologynotes.com/strategies-for-biodiversity-conservation/>
9. <https://byjus.com/biology/biodiversity-conservation/>